

Popular Article

Artificial Induction of Lactation in Bovine

Nancy Jasrotia¹, Anju Kujur¹, Sanjana², Pradeep Chandra¹, Shashikant Gupta¹

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Animal Reproduction, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122.

²Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Biological Products, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, U.P., 243122.

Abstract

Artificial induction of lactation is a method to stimulate normal lactation by using hormones/drugs. It helps in diminishing economy losses which result due to culling and replacement on account of reproductive failure or infertility in bovine. Several drug/hormone combinations are used for induction of lactation viz. estrogen, progesterone, other hormones (prolactin and glucocorticoids) etc. The milk produced is identical in composition to that of normal calving and acceptably good for human consumption. Induced lactation can serve as valuable alternative for high producing cows with low fertility. But it should be considered as last option for initiating lactation as it involves usage of exogenous hormones/drugs.

Introduction

Milk production is an endocrine as well as exocrine function. Lactation is a combined phenomenon of milk secretion and its subsequent removal from the mammary gland. It has two components namely- lactogenesis (initiation of lactation) and galactopoiesis (maintenance of lactation).

Reports suggest that infertility and reproductive disorders affect 10-30% of lactation (Erb and Martin, 1980). Economic benefits through milk selling can be obtained from artificial induction (especially in high producing cows) besides establishing normal reproductive cycle in anestrus cows. The population of stray cattle and buffalo will also be reduced following their rehabilitation.

Hormones/Drugs used for Induced Lactation

Hormones play a central role in the development and functioning of mammary gland. There are various methods of inducing lactation in infertile cows by using a combination of estrogen and progesterone. Addition of other hormones/drugs (prolactin, glucocorticoids, reserpine, etc) along with estrogen-progesterone for the onset of galactogenesis, further enhances milk yield during induced lactation (Tucker, 2000)

Estrogen and Progesterone Estrogen initiates lactogenesis in cattle at parturition by a) causing release of prolactin from the anterior pituitary gland and b) increasing the number of prolactin receptors in cells of mammary gland. Progesterone (P4) regulates lobulo-alveolar growth and blocks lactogenesis during pregnancy in several ways. It blocks glucocorticoid receptors in mammary tissues suppressing the lactogenic activity of glucocorticoids. The removal of progesterone block, luteolysis or parturition allows the onset of lactogenesis indicating the use of **prostaglandin PGF2 α** .

Prolactin along with estrogen and progesterone is required for lactogenesis. Prolactin levels surge several hours before parturition which is necessary for full lactogenesis in bovine.

Glucocorticoids: Cortisol, the major glucocorticoid in bovine helps in mammary gland development by alveolar cell differentiation of mammary gland. Glucocorticoids compete with P4 for binding sites on mammary epithelial cell. Increase in glucocorticoids displaces P4 from mammary cell receptors, thus reducing the P4 block to prolactin receptor synthesis. Addition of prolactin enhances milk yield in induced lactations.

Induced lactation protocols based on steroids are currently considered illegal because of consumer safety issues due to presence of hormones in milk.

Exogenous reserpine causes rise in blood prolactin concentration lasting for several hours in bovine.

Exogenous PGF2 α can be used after the initial estrogen-progesterone therapy to induce luteolysis and depress circulating P4 levels during glucocorticoid and reserpine administration.

Somatotropin (bST): The effect of pituitary extracts (cattle) on milk yield in dairy cows was first reported by Asimov and Krouze in 1937. Young (1947) further demonstrated that somatotropin was the galactopoeitic factor in pituitary extracts that stimulated milk yield. bST directly affects the receptors for endogenous bST located in hepatocytes and fat tissue and thus regulates the use and absorption of nutrients.

Thyroproteins: It is a hormone containing thyroxine or an iodinated amino acid which has thyroxine-like properties. Its feeding causes increase in milk production but results in marked reduction in body weight, longer calving intervals and increases in services per conception rate. Thus, it might best be utilized in overly fat cows after peak lactation.

Induction Protocols: Numerous protocols have been used successfully till date. A few have been listed below:

1. **Day1-7:** Estradiol 17- β & Progesterone @ 0.1 & 0.25mg/kg BW/day respectively.
Day9-12: Reserpine (2 mg) twice a day.
Hand milking from 10th day onwards (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973)
2. **Day1-7:** Estradiol 17- β & Progesterone @ 0.1 & 0.25 mg/kg BW/day
Day9-12: Reserpine (2 mg) twice a day
Day 18, 19 & 20: Dexamethasone (20 mg/day).
Lactation successfully induced between day 9 & 14. (Dabas and Sud, 1989)
3. **Day 1, 8 and 21:** Bovine somatotropin (500mg) along with Estradiol 17 β & Progesterone.
(Mellado et al., 2006)
4. **Day 1 to 7:** Estradiol-17 β (0.1 mg/kg) and progesterone (0.1 mg/kg) dissolved in absolute alcohol and administered subcutaneously in the neck during and over a period of 7-14 days.
Day 8: Udder stimulation (massage) started on and continued till the udder was full
Day 23 to 24: milking started (Singh et al., 2002)
5. **Day 1-** PGF2 α Lutalyse (25 mg) I/M
Day 10- PGF2 α Lutalyse (25 mg) I/M
Day 11-17- (0.1 mg of 17 β —Estradiol and 0.25 mg of progesterone dispensed per kg body weight of the animal). S/C
Day 18- PGF2 α Lutalyse (25 mg) I/M
Day 19-22- Reserpine (5 mg/day) and dexamethasone (20 mg/day) I/M (Ramgattie et al., 2014)

Points to consider: A frequent and thorough udder massage is a necessary requirement. Frequent milking should commence as soon as any udder secretion starts. Massage of udder and frequent milking stimulates the release of hormones from hypophysis for mammary gland development and milk synthesis. The milk of treated animal should not be consumed for about 30 days from the commencement of hormonal therapy owing to secretion of hormones in the milk. Treated animals require separate housing facility as they may exhibit signs of heat. A dry period of not less than 50 days should be given between two artificially induced lactations.

In conclusion, artificial induction of lactation can be used as an alternative to normal lactation as it helps in reducing culling losses in herd and increasing profits. Also, the milk from induced lactation is acceptable for human consumption and no side effects have been reported.

References

- Asimov. G. J., and N. K. Krouze. 1937. The lactogenic preparations from the anterior pituitary and the increase of milk yield in cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 20:289.
- Dabas Y.P.S. and Sud S. C. 1989. Successive induction of lactation in cattle. *Asian Australas. J. Anim.Sci.* 2 (4):571-574.
- Erb, R.E., E.L. Monk, T.A. Mollett, P.V. Malven, and C.J. Callahan. 1976 a. Estrogen, progesterone, prolactin, and other changes associated with bovine lactation induced with estradiol-17 β and progesterone. *J. Anim. Sci.* 42:644.
- Ludri R S, Singh M and Nair S. Induction of lactation in infertile indigenous cow and buffalo. Printed at NDRI press 11/5-96/2000
- Mellado M., Nazarre, E., Olivares L. 2006. Milk production and reproductive performance of cows induced into lactation and treated with bovine somatotropin. *Animal Science*, v.82, p.555-559,
- Ramgattie R, Siew N, Diptee M, Stoute V, Knights M. 2014. Effect of mammary stimulation on dairy cows and heifers exposed to a lactation induction protocol. *Open Journal of Animal Sciences.* 4 (1): 1- 12
- Singh, M., R.S. Ludri and S. Nair (2002). Milk production and reproductive performance of Murrah buffaloes (*Bubalus bubalis*) hormonally induced into lactation. *Indian J. Dairy Sci.* 55(1): 30-35.
- Smith, K.L. and Schanbacher F. L. 1973. Hormone induced lactation in the bovine I. Lactational performance following injections of 17 β -estradiol and progesterone. *Journal Dairy Science.* 56: 738- 743.
- Tucker, HA. (2000). Hormones, mammary growth, and lactation: a 41-year perspective. *J. Dairy Sci.*,83: 874-882.
- Young F.G. 1947. Experimental stimulation (galactopoiesis) of lactation. *Br. Med. Bull.*, 5, p. 155

